

Variations in the definition and perceived importance of positive resection margins in patients with colorectal cancer – an EYSAC international survey

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Colon cancer

Rectal cancer

Microscopically positive margins

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Microscopically positive resection margins (R1) are associated with poorer outcomes in patients with colorectal cancer. However, different definitions of R1 margins exist. It is unclear to what extent the definitions used in everyday clinical practice differ within and between nations. This study sought to investigate variations in the definition of R1 margins in colorectal cancer and the importance of margin status in clinical decision-making.

Materials and methods: A 14-point survey was developed by members of The European Society of Surgical Oncology (ESSO) Youngs Surgeons and Alumni Club (EYSAC) Research Academy targeting all members of the multidisciplinary team (MDT) treating patients with colorectal cancer. The survey was distributed on social media, in ESSO's monthly newsletter and via national societies.

Results: In total, 137 responses were received. Most respondents were from Europe (89.7%), with the majority from Denmark (56.9%). Less than 2/3 of respondents defined R1 margins as the presence of viable cancer cells ≤ 1 mm of the margin. Only 60% reported that subdivisions of R1 margins (primary tumour vs tumour deposit vs metastatic lymph node) are routinely available. More than 20% of respondents reported that pathology reports are not routinely reviewed at MDT meetings. Less than half of respondents considered margin status in decision-making for type and duration of adjuvant chemotherapy in Stage III colon cancer.

Conclusion: The definitions and perceived clinical importance of microscopically positive margins in patients with colorectal cancer appear to vary. Adoption of an international dataset for pathology reporting may help to standardise current practices.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejso.2023.107072>

Received 24 May 2023; Received in revised form 3 August 2023; Accepted 9 September 2023

Available online 11 September 2023

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1. Introduction

Surgery remains the cornerstone of treatment for patients diagnosed with localised colorectal cancer [1,2]. Here the aim is to perform an en-bloc resection of the affected portion of bowel along with its associated lymph nodes, and achieve clear surgical margins, in particular with regard to circumferential or non-peritonealised margins. The finding of viable cancer cells at or close to the surgical margin when all visible disease has been removed (i.e. microscopically positive margins) is associated with poorer oncological outcomes. In rectal cancer, patients with microscopically positive margins after surgery have higher risks of both local and distant recurrence and are consequently more likely to die from their disease than patients with clear surgical margins [3–5]. However, recent studies have also demonstrated that similar associations exist in patients undergoing surgery for colon cancer [6–8]. Furthermore, the nature of margin involvement also seems to be of importance, with different patterns of recurrence observed in patients with microscopically positive margins to the primary tumour when compared to those involved by metastatic lymph nodes or tumour deposits [9]. As such, margin status should be considered an important prognostic factor in patients undergoing potentially curative surgery for colorectal cancer and influence the decisions regarding adjuvant chemotherapy.

However, variations in the definition of microscopically positive resection margins have been noted in the literature. The R classification was originally suggested in 1977 by the American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) and defined a microscopically positive margin as the presence of cancer cells directly at the resection margin [10]. After demonstrating the importance of lateral margin involvement in patients with rectal cancer, Quirke et al. proposed an alternative system referring to the circumferential resection margin (CRM), whereby microscopically positive margins were defined as the presence of cancer cells at or within 1 mm of the CRM [11,12]. Variations of this definition have also been described, for example using a distance of 2 mm rather than 1 mm to the CRM to define positive margins [4]. With the aim of reducing possible confusion between various definitions, a uniform R classification has been proposed, whereby microscopically positive margins are defined as either directly involved by cancer cells (R1-dir) or where there is minimal distance ($R1 \leq 1$ mm) from cancer cells to the margin [13].

However, the extent to which the definitions of margin status used in everyday clinical practice vary on intra- and international levels is currently unknown. The current study sought to investigate variations in the definition and perceived clinical importance of microscopically positive resection margins using an online survey.

2. Methods

This survey was designed by members of The European Society of Surgical Oncology Young Surgeons and Alumni Club (EYSAC) Research Academy. The design included details regarding the demographics of the respondent (career grade, specialty, geographic location); the definition of resection margins; and the role of margin status in determining the need for further treatment following surgery. The survey was aimed at all members of the multidisciplinary team (MDT) involved in the treatment of patients with colorectal cancer.

The first draft of the questionnaire was tested in a pilot study at a single institution to confirm the suitability of the questions and the validity of the response options. Minor alterations were then made for a final draft, which was approved by all members of the study group. A copy of the final 14-point questionnaire is provided in the supplementary data. The link to the final survey was distributed online via social media, promoted by the ESSO and EYSAC profiles, and via the ESSO email newsletter. The link was also distributed nationally by members of the EYSAC research academy. The survey was open for a 6-month period between May–October 2022. The survey link included a short statement

on the goals of the survey and clarified that all responses would be anonymous. Ethical approval was not required for this study.

After the survey was closed, all responses were collated, and descriptive analyses were performed. Survey responses that were not entirely complete were included in the analyses of completed fields but excluded from those that were not completed. In order to investigate intra- and inter-national variation in responses, comparative analyses were performed between respondents from Denmark, which had the most respondents, to a mixed pool of responses from other nations.

3. Results

The survey page was visited by a total of 143 times, with 137 individuals completing at least part of the survey (95.8%). The entire survey was completed by 99 respondents (69.2%). The majority of respondents were from European nations (123 responses, 89.7%), with the most responses received from Denmark (78 responses, 56.9%) (Fig. 1). Further details of the geographical location of respondents are provided in Table 1. While surgery was the most common specialty (75 responses, 54.7%), variation in the type of respondent was noted according to geographic location. Respondents from Denmark were a mixed group comprised mainly of pathologists (60.3%), surgeons (26.9%) and radiologists (9.0%), whereas respondents from other nations were primarily surgeons (91.5%). The majority of respondents were consultants/attendings (103 responses, 76.3%), with no differences in the grade of respondents noted according to geographical location.

3.1. Definitions of margin status

The majority of respondents reported that an assessment of margin status was always included in pathology reports after colorectal cancer resection at their institution (97/104 responses, 93.3%). However, variations were noted in the definition of microscopically positive margins between respondents (Fig. 2a). While the most common definition was the presence of viable cancer cells ≤ 1 mm of the margin, more than 1/3 of respondents reported an alternative definition. Variations were also noted in the reporting of subdivisions of microscopically positive margins, with only 59.1% of respondents (81/137 responses) routinely receiving information about close margins to tumour deposits and only 55.5% (76/137 responses) receiving information about close margins to metastatic lymph nodes. Interestingly, the use of different definitions of microscopically positive margins for colon and rectal cancers within the same institution was reported by 19.0% of respondents, with a similar proportion of respondents (16.7%) replying that the reporting of subdivisions of resection margins differs between these two groups.

Greater variation in the definitions of margin status were noted between nations rather than within a single nation. Whereas the majority of respondents from Denmark defined microscopically positive margins as the presence of viable cancer cells ≤ 1 mm of the margin, alternative definitions were significantly more common in respondents from other nations (Fig. 2b–c, $p < 0.001$). Respondents from other nations were also more likely to report the use of different definitions of margin status according to tumour location (37.5% versus 1.9%, $p < 0.001$) and less likely to report that pathology reports included details regarding the nature of microscopically positive margins, be they to the primary tumour, tumour deposits or lymph node metastases (81.6% versus 98.1%, $p < 0.001$).

3.2. Impact of microscopically positive margins

While the majority of respondents (97/100, 97.0%) reported that MDT meetings for colorectal cancer are routinely held at their institution, only 78.0% reported that post-operative pathology reports were routinely reviewed at these meetings. Variations were also reported in the pathological factors used by MDTs to determine the type and

Fig. 1. Demographics of the survey respondents. (A) Specialty. (B) Career grade. (C) Geographical location.

Table 1
Geographical location of survey respondents.

Continent	Nation	Number of respondents
Europe	All	123
	Denmark	78
	United Kingdom	8
	Spain	5
	Romania	4
	Serbia	4
	Bulgaria	3
	Italy	3
	France	2
	Ireland	2
	Poland	2
	Sweden	2
	Turkey	2
	Albania	1
	Azerbaijan	1
	Belgium	1
	Germany	1
	Greece	1
	Lithuania	1
Portugal	1	
Ukraine	1	
South America		5
Asia		4
Africa		3
North America		2
Oceania		1

duration of adjuvant chemotherapy in patients with Stage III colorectal cancer (Fig. 3a). Less than half of all respondents (66/137, 48.2%) reported that microscopically positive margins influenced decisions regarding adjuvant chemotherapy in these patients. The importance of different pathological factors in this decision-making process differed according to geographical location, with microscopically positive margins, extramural venous invasion, lymphatic invasion and perineural

invasion less likely to be considered by respondents from Denmark when compared to other nations (Fig. 3b–c).

The perceived importance of microscopically positive margins also varied. While the majority of respondents were of the opinion that margin status was of clinical importance (81/99 responses, 81.8%), a minority stated that positive margins were only clinically relevant if they were related to the primary tumour (7/99 responses, 7.1%) or the margin was directly involved (9.1%, 9/99 responses).

4. Discussion

This survey provides an insight into variations in the definitions of microscopically positive margins used in everyday clinical practice and the importance attributed to margin status by clinicians. One of the study’s most interesting findings is the marked variation in how microscopically positive margins were defined by respondents. While the majority of respondents defined these margins as the presence of cancer cells ≤ 1 mm of the margin, which is in keeping with the proposed uniform definition of margin status [13], roughly 1 in 5 respondents defined a positive margin as being directly involved by cancer cells, in keeping with the previous AJCC definition [10]. Greater variation in the definition of margin status was noted between rather than within nations, with alternative definitions reported by only 1 in 10 respondents from Denmark compared with 1 in 3 respondents from other nations.

Several studies have previously investigated variations in the reporting of margin status in patients with colorectal cancer, on both national and international levels. In an audit of over 1,200 specimens in Wales, margin status was only included in just over half of all reports on rectal cancer specimens [14]. Better results were seen in a later audit from the Netherlands, where margin status was reported in 85% of rectal cancer specimens [15]. Similar rates of reporting were noted from a more recent international survey of pathologists, the majority of whom were from European nations [16]. However, there have been very few studies that have investigated variations in the definition of margin

Fig. 2. Variations responses to the question “How are microscopically positive margins defined at your institution?” (A) All respondents. (B) Respondents from Denmark. (C) Respondents from the rest of the world.

Fig. 3. Responses to the question “In patients with Stage III colorectal cancer, which pathological factors are used by your multidisciplinary team to determine the type and duration of adjuvant chemotherapy?” (A) All respondents. (B) Respondents from Denmark. (C) Respondents from the rest of the world. * denotes statistically significant differences between respondents from Denmark versus the rest of the world.

status. In a meta-analysis including over 200 studies of pre-operative radiotherapy or chemoradiotherapy in patients with rectal cancer, only 14 studies reported data on margin status, with only 10 of those studies using the definition of cancer cells ≤ 1 mm of the margin [17]. It should, however, be noted that the studies included in this meta-analysis were performed between 1993 and 2005, so this may not be a true reflection of current clinical practice.

Discrepancies in the definition of margin status are a cause for concern, as a lack of common terminology will lead to several obvious negative consequences. The first is in the comparison of treatment and patient outcomes, both between different institutions and different nations. Margin status is often used as a marker of surgical quality, which cannot be reliably compared between institutions if different definitions are used. Furthermore, given the association of microscopically positive margins with both local and distant recurrence, a stricter definition of margin involvement (i.e. direct involvement only) will lead to the appearance of ‘better’ surgery, as the R0 rate will be higher, that is paradoxically associated with higher recurrence rates. A further issue lies in the performance of clinical trials. Margin status may be used either as an inclusion criterion for trials of adjuvant therapies or as an outcome, surrogate or otherwise, for trials of neoadjuvant therapies. Variations in the definition of margin status can not only complicate international recruitment to such studies but also limit the widespread interpretation and adoption of their findings.

The current study suggests that more needs to be done to standardise the definitions and reporting of microscopically positive resection margins in patients with colorectal cancer. It is particular importance to clarify what is meant by an R0 resection and how this compares to a negative CRM. Although these descriptions are often thought to be synonymous, this depends on the precise definition of a R0 margin, which can lead to issues that are well summarised in the paper by Wittekind et al. [13]. An international core dataset for pathology reporting in colorectal cancer has recently been developed and may help to address this variation [18]. Margin status is one of the 18 core elements in this dataset, which recommends that positive margins are defined as the presence of cancer cell ≤ 1 mm of the margin.

Disappointingly, these recommendations infer that positive margins in colon cancer are rare and of lesser importance than in rectal cancer, and that margins that are close to but not directly involved by metastatic lymph nodes should not be regarded as positive as they are not associated with increased recurrence risks. However, recent studies suggest that positive margins in patients with colon cancer may be more common than previously thought. In a study of $>4,000$ patients, the rate of positive margins (≤ 1 mm) to the primary tumour was similar in colon and rectum cancer specimens (5.2% and 6.3%, respectively) [8]. Positive margins to metastatic lymph nodes or tumour deposits were also common, reported in 10.7% of colon cancer specimens and 11.2% of rectal cancer specimens. In a subsequent study, positive margins to metastatic lymph nodes or tumour deposits was associated with an increased risk of local and distant recurrence when compared to clear

margins in patients with rectal cancer [9]. Although not associated with local recurrence, a similar increase in the risk of distant recurrence was observed when positive margins to metastatic lymph nodes or tumour deposits was compared to clear margins in patients with colon cancer. These novel findings suggest that positive margins are common and of clinical importance in patients with colon cancer, and that of positive margins to tumour deposits or metastatic lymph nodes pose similar risks to those to the primary tumour.

Another interesting finding of the current study was the variation in the factors that are used to determine the type and duration of adjuvant therapy in patients with Stage III colon cancer. Current guidelines recommend a combination of fluoropyrimidine and oxaliplatin for 3 months in low-risk patients and 6 months of an oxaliplatin-based combination therapy in high-risk patients, whereby T and N stage may be used to determine the risk of relapse [1]. Both factors were reported by the majority of respondents. However, significant variation was noted in the use of extramural venous invasion, lymphatic invasion and perineural invasion, particularly between Denmark and other nations. While recognised as important prognostic factors in patients with Stage II disease, their role in Stage III disease is less clear [19]. Current Danish national guidelines recommend stratifying patients with Stage III disease into low- and high-risk group according to T and N stage alone, which may explain the low rates of respondents from this country who consider these factors when deciding on the type and duration of adjuvant therapy [20]. There is mounting evidence that R1 margins are associated with poorer oncological outcomes and that this association may be independent of other histopathological risk factors [6–9]. Although patients with R1 margins were not included in randomised trials of adjuvant therapies [21–23], it would seem reasonable to consider margin status as an additional prognostic factor, particularly in patients who would otherwise be considered low risk. Despite not being specifically recommended in current guidelines, it is interesting to note that more than half of respondents use this factor in their decision-making processes.

This study has several limitations. With the exception of Denmark, the number of respondents from each individual country was small, which limited the comparisons of responses between different nations. However, by comparing the responses from a single nation to a mixed pool of nations, we believe some meaningful insights can be made as to the extent of intra- and international variation between respondents. It should be noted that the majority of respondents were from Europe. As such, these findings may be less representative of current practices in the rest of the world. Discrepancies were also noted between the type of respondents from Denmark and other nations, which could have potentially confounded some of the results. The overwhelming majority of respondents from other nations were surgeons, whereas a greater mix of specialties was noted from Denmark. It is interesting to note that despite this, the responses from Denmark were generally more uniform. The number of responses from oncologists was low and the extent to which more responses from the specialty would have altered the results

is unknown, particularly with regard to adjuvant therapy. Finally, the results of this survey are only indicative of differences in the definitions and perceived importance of margin status, which should ideally be validated with international audits.

In conclusion, the definitions and perceived clinical importance of microscopically positive margins in patients with colorectal cancer appear to vary. Adoption of an international dataset for pathology reporting may help to standardise current practices. However, recent studies suggest that positive margins in colon cancer and those to metastatic lymph nodes are of greater importance than previously thought. As such, these factors should be routinely reported in all colorectal cancer specimens.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

H.G. Smith: Conceptualization, Methodology, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **N.H. Schlesinger:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **C. Qvortrup:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **D. Chiranth:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **D. Lundon:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **A. Ben-Yaacov:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **C. Caballero:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **I. Suppan:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **J. Herrera Kok:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **C.J. Holmberg:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **H. Mohan:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **G. Montagna:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **N. Santrac:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **R. Sayyed:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Y. Schrage:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **O. Sgarbura:** Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **W. Ceelen:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **L. Lorenzon:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **A. Brandl:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declarations of competing interest

The authors have no declarations of interest

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejso.2023.107072>.

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